

Interview guideline

1 Assess the background and professional qualifications

1.1 How long have you been working in this company?

Answer:

1.2 What is your academic qualification?

Answer:

1.3 Which professional qualifications (certificates...) do you have?

Answer:

1.4 How many years did you spend in software development projects?

Answer:

1.5 How many years of experience do you have in using agile methodologies?

Answer:

1.6 Which roles in agile methodologies have you worked so far?

Answer:

1.7 What is your actual role in your team?

Answer:

2 Assess the team and company structure from a cultural view

2.1 How would you describe the company culture?

Answer:

2.2 Which nationalities exist in your team?

Answer:

2.3 Would you say your team is consisting of multicultural people?

Answer:

2.4 Is your team distributed to different locations of your company?

3 Assess the used agile methodology / methodologies

3.1 Which methodology is used in your team / project?

Answer:

3.2 Are you doing daily stand up meetings?

Answer:

3.3 Are you doing review meetings?

Answer:

3.4 Are you doing planning meetings?

Answer:

3.5 Are you doing retrospective meetings?

Answer:

3.6 How long is an iteration planned?

Answer:

3.7 Who is managing the product backlog?

Answer:

3.8 Do dedicated Scrum Master for your team exist?

Answer:

4 Assess the impact of culture to agile methodologies

a. Power distance:

4.1 Describe the role of the Scrum Master during the Planning, Daily and Grooming Meetings

Answer:

4.2 Describe the role of the Product Owner during the Planning, Daily and Grooming Meetings

Answer:

4.3 Does the management participate to the meetings?

Answer:

4.3.1 If yes, does the management have an impact / talk on those meetings?

Answer:

4.4 Did you notice that the management influence the agile process?

Answer:

4.5 Did you notice that the management influence projects (e.g. on Estimations, Requirements, Goals)?

Answer:

4.6 Is the team fully self-organized?

Answer:

4.7 Who is interacting with the customer? (PO, Management, ...)

Answer:

4.8 Is there a group spokesperson while running different team sessions?

Answer:

b. Individualism:

4.9 How is the working atmosphere in your team?

Answer:

4.10 Please describe the team structure?

Answer:

4.11 Is the team working together on sprint goals?

Answer:

4.12 Is the team working as a “team” (e.g. discuss technical problems or challenges together)?

Answer:

4.13 Is the team striving for a common optimization of the working method (e.g. in retrospective meetings)?

Answer:

4.14 Do you have the opportunity to address improvement options in retrospective meetings?

Answer:

4.15 Do you have regular activities with your team outside of work (e.g. joint dinner)?

Answer:

c. Uncertainly avoidance:

4.16 Would you say, that you are estimating the effort in a conservative way?

Answer:

4.17 Do you communicate open questions when they are exist?

Answer:

4.18 Are you satisfied with the degree of documentation which is used in your project / team?

Answer:

4.19 What do you think about Story cards and Kanban boards? Is this documentation sufficient from your perspective?

Answer:

4.20 While doing estimations: Are the often dedicated estimations in your team?

Answer:

4.20.1 When there are differences in your team estimations: Is the team discussing these challenges to find a consensus on an estimation?

Answer:

4.21 While doing daily stand up meetings / planning meetings / ...: Are you communicate challenges or problems to your team when you identify those?

Answer:

4.22 Are you doing a Grooming meeting with your Product Owner?

Answer:

4.23 Do you have a requirements specification document?

Answer:

4.24 During the sprint: Is the sprint board always up to date?

Answer:

4.25 During the sprint: How are communicate problems with sprint goal / milestones / deadlines?

Answer: